

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Stakeholders' views on the agricultural practices applied in potato cultivation in the Nemoral area: obstacles and effective solutions

Identifying the most relevant current agri-environmental problems of potato crop and the priority needs of end-users is necessary to assess the practical potential for integrating more sustainable farming practices into the different farming systems. In Nemoral area, 29 stakeholders were surveyed: potato farmers, agricultural technical advisors and other stakeholders such as researchers or administrators. The most serious agronomic problems identified were low and variable yields, rainfall scarcity in growing period, soil compaction and high incidence of fungal diseases. In order to tackle those agronomic problems, the most important priorities were to improve the soil structure to improve aeration, water retention and rooting, increasing soil fertility, mobilizing nutrients during crop development, increased soil organic matter as well as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases. The most effective farming

practices according to the survey results were conventional and minimum tillage, organic matter addition and use of green manure. In addition, crop diversification and addition of organic matter were mentioned as the most effective techniques to conserve the soil. Crop diversification is relevant for the control pests and diseases as well. According to the stakeholders, lack of knowledge among farmers about the effectiveness of practices, cost-effectiveness or lack of regulations to encourage the application of these techniques hinder the adoption of more sustainable techniques. The fact that the advisors work for distributors of agricultural inputs is also seen as a barrier. Therefore, there is a need to research, advise and keep farmers informed in order to steer agriculture towards profitable and sustainable production systems.

1. Potato field. Author: Sutri, M.

KEYWORDS

Soil conservation, tillage, agronomic problems, potato cultivation.

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